

Exploring the Effect of Organizational Climate on the Emotional Health of Teachers: A Case Study of Colleges in Islamabad

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Abstract

Organizational climate is related to the traits which are contained within the scope of work and they can affect the behavior of members working in the organization. Mental health is a state of emotional and social well-being in which the individual realizes his own abilities, can manage the normal stresses of life, and can work effectively. Emotional health plays important role in the professional life of an individual and it effects job tasks as well. The role of a teacher is very important as he directly effects the emotions of the students. Thus a teacher needs to be emotionally healthy and in this connection organizational climate plays vital role. The purpose of the study was to see the effect of organizational climate on the emotional health of college teachers. The objectives of the study were to measure the effect of managerial competence, cohesion, and participation on the emotional health of teachers. This was a causal comparative research which was quantitative research in nature. The sample of the study consisted of randomly selected 50 college teachers, 25 teachers from public sector and 25 from private sector working in Islamabad Pakistan. Two structured questionnaire were used to measure organizational climate of colleges and emotional health of teachers. The data collection was done online and it was analyzed by descriptive statistics. Findings showed that the climate of the organization had significant effect on the emotional health of teachers. It was recommended that the Government, educational institutes of educators, community of educational providers, and teacher professional organizations may work together to improve organizational climate of educational institutions.

Key words: *organizational climate, emotional health, college teachers, cohesion, managerial competence*

Introduction

Owens and Valesky (2015) state that organizational climate is the study of perceptions that individuals have about various aspects of the environment in the organization. Organizational climate is related to the traits which are contained within the scope of work and they can affect the behavior of members working in the organization (Permarupan et al, 2013). The climate within an organization affects the behavior and attitudes of members within the organization (Lin & Lee, 2017). So organizational climate plays important role in making the atmosphere favorable for a specific organization. Mental health is a state of emotional and social well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can manage the normal stresses of life, can work effectively, and is able to play a role in his or her community. Mental health or emotional health is influenced by individual, biological and psychological factors, social interactions, societal structures & cultural values. The progress of a nation is determined by the progress of education and the progress of education is determined by the qualities of its teachers. So the teacher is the key person to make the educational system a success, so it is necessary that he should be provided with all facilities to assist him so that he/she may fulfil the duties earnestly and as it is universally accepted that a dissatisfied worker cannot do full justice with his/her job. The role of a teacher is very important as he directly effects the emotions of the students. Thus a teacher needs to be emotionally healthy and in this connection organizational climate plays vital role. This study is undertaken keeping in view this need.

Organizational Climate:

Owen (1998) is of view that the opinion of individuals about different aspects of the atmosphere in the organization can be classified as organizational climate. Katz and Kahn (1996) say that the environment in an organization that reveals the kind of people who work in the organization, the work progress, modes of

communication and the implementation of authority in the organization makes the organizational climate. Litwin and Stringer (1968) state that organizational climate is actually set of characteristics of the work environment which is based on the observations of the individuals who constitute the environment and ultimately their ideology drive their behavior. A prosperous organization has its clear vision and objectives. Its members work together efficiently and actively to achieve goals. (Gibson and Ivancevich, 1997). Bhagat and Steers (2012) state that organizational climate can be seen from the perceptions of the members of the organization and from the relationship between activities of the organization and behavior of the management. So more often the psychological configuration of an organization is illustrated by the term organizational climate Every educational institution has its own climate .There are various kinds of interactions which can take place in any educational institution but the interaction between teachers and the principal defines or determines educational atmosphere.

Emotional health

Barry (2011) states that mental health is the emotional and social appropriateness of a person, in which he/she can identify his capacities and tendencies of working with the stress of daily routine life and can perform his job in a much better way and can contribute in prosperity of the society. Our psychological, social and emotional stability is called mental or emotional health. It affects our thinking pattern, attitudes and Behaviour. It also helps us in determining how we handle stress, relate to others, and make choices and decisions. Mental health is important at every stage of life, from childhood to adulthood. George (2000) is of opinion that People are not alike in recognition and expression of their emotions. So people respond differently in same situation and emotionally healthy individuals are more successful in life as they understand their surroundings and they know how to tackle uncertain situations wisely. So those individuals who have ability to recognize and respond to their emotions are understood by others in better way. Moreover they can effectively manage and lead the people around them when they recognize and understand the emotions of others with empathy (Salovey & Mayer, 1990).

Now mental and emotional health is considered to be a medical phenomenon and psychological and sociological process. Being in the state of free of stress and depression is not mere sign of emotional health it rather includes being free of mental illness and possession of positive traits. Mental health also influences some other traits like emotional intelligence, self-concept, self-awareness and self-efficacy (Gupta.g & Kumar sushil 2010). There are some factors which effect emotional health such as biological & psychological factors, social interactions, societal structures & cultural values and norms (Barry, 2011, Lehtinen 2008).

Review of previous related studies

Mistry (1985) in his study concluded that motivation had positive effect on job satisfaction, involvement and overall satisfaction of employees or workers, while a strict control had negative impact. Singh (1985) conducted a research in which he selected three types of schools on the basis of their performances: high performance schools, average performance schools and low performance schools. In this study he chose disengagement, aloofness, esprit, psychological hindrance, consideration, humanized thrust and production emphasis as different dimensions of organizational climate. He concluded that high performance schools showed lower scores on aspects like psychological hindrance and disengagement while higher on thrust, esprit and as compared to the average performance schools and low performance schools.

Appleberry and Hoy (1969) in his study on climate of school and performance of teachers acknowledged that a pleasant atmosphere of the school resulted in better performance of the teachers regarding controlling the students. Hayat (1998) in his research concluded that factors like size of faculty , and long service in the college and good performance of teachers in the classrooms was directly related to the job satisfaction at college which was due to good atmosphere of college, that was open and autonomous. Hesel, Aurbach, and Willower (1969) in their study established that principal's traits like thrust, consideration, and production emphasis, as perceived by teachers, produced optimism whereas trait like hindrance produced pessimism in the teachers.

Statement of the Problem:

Emotional health plays important role in the professional life of an individual and it effects job tasks as well. The purpose of the study was to see the effect of organizational climate on the emotional health of teachers.

Methodology

This was a causal comparative research which was quantitative research in nature. This was conducted to see the effect of organizational climate on emotional health of teachers. The study was intended to be carried out keeping in view the following objectives:

1-To measure the effect of managerial competence on the emotional health of teachers. 2- To assess effect of cohesion on the emotional health of teachers.

3- To evaluate effect of participation on the emotional health of teachers. Hypothesis for the study were:

H0 1: Managerial competence has no significant effect on the emotional health of teachers.

H0 2: Cohesion has no significant effect on the emotional health of teachers. H03: Participation has no significant effect on the emotional health of teachers.

The sample of the study consisted of randomly selected 50 college teachers, 25 teachers from public sector and 25 from private sector working in Islamabad, Pakistan. Two structured questionnaire based upon 5 point Likert scale were used to measure organizational climate of colleges and emotional health of teachers. The data collection was done online. The data collected were tabulated and analyzed using descriptive statistical measure (percentage & mean).

Findings

Table-1 Mean scores of responses of teachers, working in public sector, on indicators of organizational climate.

N	Managerial competence	Cohesion	Participation	Mean
25	70	75	25	56

This table shows that mean scores of responses of teachers, working in public sector, on indicators of organizational climate is 56.

Table-2 Percentages of scores of responses of teachers, working in public sector, on indicators of organizational climate.

N	Managerial competence	Cohesion	Participation	Percentage
25	57%	58%	20%	44%

This table shows that the percentage of scores of responses of teachers, working in public sector, on indicators of organizational climate is 44%.

Table-3 Mean scores of responses of teachers, working in public sector, on indicators of emotional health

N	Self-Awareness	Esprit	Resilience	Positive Relations with others	Mean
25	60	80	70	60	67

This table shows that mean scores of responses of teachers, working in public sector, on indicators of emotional health is 67.

Table -4 Percentages of scores of responses of teachers, working in public sector, on indicators of emotional health

N	Self-Awareness	Esprit	Resilience	Positive Relations with others	Percentage
25	48%	65%	56%	48%	56%

This table shows that percentage of scores of responses of teachers, working in public sector, on indicators of emotional health is 56%.

Table-5 Mean scores of responses of teachers, working in private sector, on indicators of organizational climate.

N	Managerial competence	Cohesion	Participation	Mean
25	85	40	20	48

This table shows that mean scores of responses of teachers, working in private sector, on indicators of organizational climate is 48.

Table-6 Percentages of scores of responses of teachers, working in private sector, on indicators of organizational climate.

N	Managerial competence	Cohesion	Participation	Percentage
25	66%	31%	16%	40%

This table shows that percentage of scores of responses of teachers, working in private sector, on indicators of organizational climate is 40%.

Table- 7 Mean scores of responses of teachers, working in private sector, on indicators of emotional health

N	Self-Awareness	Esprit	Resilience	Positive Relations with others	Mean
25	45	40	30	35	37

This table shows that mean scores of responses of teachers, working in private sector, on indicators of emotional health is 37.

Table-8 Percentages of scores of responses of teachers, working in private sector, on indicators of emotional health

N	Self-Awareness	Esprit	Resilience	Positive Relations with others	Percentage
25	36%	32%	25%	30%	32%

This table shows that percentage of scores of responses of teachers, working in private sector, on indicators of emotional health is 32%.

Table 9- Mean scores and percentages of scores of teachers of public sector on Organizational Climate & Emotional Health

N	25	
Variables	Mean	Percentage
Organizational Climate	56	44%
Emotional Health	67	56%

This table shows that mean score of responses of teachers, working in public sector, on organizational climate is 56 and on emotional health is 67. The percentage of scores on organizational climate is 44% and on emotional health is 56%.

Table 10 - Mean scores and percentages of scores of teachers of private sector on organizational climate & emotional health

N	25	
Variables	Mean	Percentage
Organizational Climate	48	40%
Emotional Health	37	32%

This table shows that mean score of responses of teachers, working in private sector, on organizational climate is 48 and on emotional health is 37. The percentage of scores on organizational climate is 40% and on emotional health is 32%.

Table 11 - Comparison of mean scores and percentages of scores of teachers of public sector and private sector on both variables

Sectors	Public Sector		Private Sector	
N	25		25	
Variables	Mean	Percentage	Mean	Percentage
Organizational Climate	56	44%	48	40%
Emotional Health	67	56%	37	32%

Results and Discussion

Findings of the study showed that that mean scores of responses of teachers, working in public sector, on indicators of organizational climate were managerial competence 70, cohesion among coworkers 75, participation 25 and the percentage of scores showed that 57% respondents were satisfied with managerial competence, 58% agreed that cohesion among coworkers existed and 20% agreed that participation of employees was ensured in decision making process. Similarly the mean scores of responses of teachers, working in public sector, on indicators of emotional health were self-awareness 60, esprit 80, resilience 70, positive relations with others 60 and percentage of scores stated that 48% respondents were well aware of their emotional states, 65% respondents were esprit, 56% had resilience and 48% had positive relations with others.

The mean scores of responses of teachers, working in private sector, on indicators of organizational climate were managerial competence 85 , cohesion among coworkers 40 , and participation 20 and percentage of scores showed that 66% respondents were satisfied with managerial competence, 31% agreed that cohesion among coworkers existed and 16% agreed that participation of employees was ensured in decision making process. Similarly the mean scores of responses of teachers, working in private sector, on indicators of emotional health were self-awareness 45, esprit 40 ,resilience 30 , positive relations with others 35 and percentage of scores stated that 36% respondents were well aware of their emotional states, 32% respondents were esprit , 25%, had resilience and 30% had positive relations with others.

The mean score of responses of teachers, working in public sector, on organizational climate was 56 and on emotional health was 67. The percentage of scores on organizational climate was 44% and on emotional health was 56%. Similarly the mean score of responses of teachers, working in private sector, on organizational climate was 48 and on emotional health was 37. The percentage of scores on organizational climate was 40% and on emotional health was 32%.

Conclusion

On the basis of analysis and interpretation of the data following findings were drawn:

- 1- The mean score of teachers, working in public sector, on different aspects of organizational climate was 56.
- 2- The mean score of teachers, working in private sector, on different aspects of organizational climate was 48.
- 3- The mean score of teachers, working in public sector, on different aspects of emotional health was 67.
- 4- The mean score of teachers, working in private sector, on different aspects of emotional health was 37.

This showed that the mean score of teachers, working in public sector, on organizational climate was 56 which was higher than mean score of teachers, working in private sector, which was 48. Similarly the mean score of teachers, working in public sector, on emotional health was 67 which was higher than mean score of teachers, working in private sector, which was 37.

From the findings it was concluded that null hypothesis which stated:

H0 1: Managerial competence has no significant effect on the emotional health of teachers. H0 2:

Cohesion has no significant effect on the emotional health of teachers.

H03: Participation has no significant effect on the emotional health of teachers, has been rejected on the basis of the findings of the study, which showed that teachers working in public sector were emotionally healthier than teachers working in private sector because organizational climate in public sector was better than in private sector. So the climate of the organization had significant effect on the emotional health of teachers.

Recommendations

The organizational climate is influenced by the strategies of the manager or administrator. So a well-prepared and professional principal can create a working climate that supports teachers to grow in their profession as an emotionally healthy person. Crash programs for training of teachers and administrators may be fruitful in this connection. The Government, educational institutes of educators, community of educational providers, and teacher professional organizations may work together and play their role significantly, to improve organizational climate of educational institutions.

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